

Teaching a Child with Down's Syndrome to Tact for Common Objects Using Prompts: A Single Case Study

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Tact is a procedure to obtain a response with the help of an object or event. In many habilitative programs for individuals with developmental disabilities, tact training is often used. In the present study, V, a 10yr old boy with Down's syndrome was taught to tact for 10 common objects using the supplemental question "what is this?" keeping all the motivating operations in place. The intervention was conducted after doing observation and collecting the baseline. Intervention consisted of echoic prompts and a prompt fading procedure. After 10 sessions of intervention, V was able to tact for 10 common objects when asked for using "what is this?" He was able to generalize the taught skill with different people and environments.

Keywords: Tact, positive reinforcement, Down's syndrome, prompts, verbal operants

A tact is said to "make contact with" the world and talks about a behavior that is under the control of any reinforcement, as mentioned in Cooper, Heron, and Heward (2007). The tact is a type of verbal operant under the functional control of a non-verbal discriminative stimulus, and it produces generalized conditioned reinforcement as discussed in Cooper, Heron, and Heward (2007). A stimulus may trigger a response, but it is the verbal community that teaches the speaker how to respond with words, as discussed in Cooper, Heron, and Heward. Tact training is a common element of many habilitative programs for individuals with developmental disabilities like Autism Spectrum Disorder and Down syndrome, etc. During tact training, it is often recommended to include the question 'What is this?' while teaching object labels, as noted by Marchese et al. (2012). Using this question does not define the feature of the tact relation, but prior research suggests that its inclusion might help to get an appropriate tact as discussed by Marchese et al. (2012).

Children with Down syndrome are at an increased risk of engaging in challenging behaviors that may be a part of the behavioral phenotype characteristics of Down syndrome. The methodology of Applied Behavior Analysis has been demonstrated to be effective with a wide range of challenging behaviors across various disabilities (Feeley & Jones, 2006). Applications to children with Down syndrome and examination of behaviorally based strategies to specifically address the unique characteristics of children with Down syndrome are limited, as discussed by Kathleen Feeley and Emiley Jones (2006). In 1989, Darsh et al. describe how Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA) strategies can be used to support individuals with Down syndrome.

The study highlights various techniques such as reinforcement, prompting, and task analysis to improve communication, learning,

and adaptive skills. It emphasizes individualized assessment and structured intervention to promote independence and reduce challenging behaviors. A paper published by Feeley and Jones (2006) demonstrated the uses of ABA to teach new skills.

This paper reports a case study and illustrates the effectiveness of ABA in increasing spontaneous comments made by a young boy who is 3 years 9 months of age. Spontaneous comments can be achieved using prompts and prompt fading procedures. Clannahan and Krantz (1999) defined prompts as "instructions, gestures, demonstrations, touches, or any other thing that we arrange or do to increase the likelihood that children will make correct responses". Echoic prompts have also been used to train tact responses. Kodak and Clements (2009) found that echoic training sessions before tact were found to be effective at increasing independent tact responses. This intervention is aimed at observing the effects of tact training for common objects on a child with Down syndrome. The procedure includes transferring the control of stimulus from verbal to non-verbal stimulus by gradually decreasing the echoic prompt.

Method

Participants

V is a 10yr old boy diagnosed with Down's syndrome by Touran Zadeh at Hoag Hospital, Newport Beach, California. Genetic tests done after birth showed that the boy had Trisomy 21. Since then, he has been receiving therapies at various centers in the USA and now in India. Now since last 1yr he has been receiving intensive behavior therapy at Total Solution Rehabilitation Society, Hyderabad, for 1 hour/day. On assessing him, his DQ was 60 and SQ was 65. He can recognize common objects, fruits, vegetables, and action words. Varun can also greet known people when asked to, but is unable to tact for common objects. As a child with Down syndrome, he faces difficulty with poor expressive language, difficulty in word retrieval, poor speech clarity due to a fatty tongue, and various other oro-motor challenges. All experimental trials were done after obtaining consent from the parents.

Materials

All experimental trials were conducted in a regular therapeutic room in one-on-one sessions where V is attending a regular behavioral

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I have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

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Table 4*Observational Sheet for IOA - Baseline*

Objects	OB1	OB2	AGR	OBS1	OBS2	AGR	OBS1	OBS2	AGR
Cup	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Ball	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	Y
Plate	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	Y
Glass	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	Y
Comb	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	Y
Car	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	Y
Chair	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	Y
Bottle	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	Y
Phone	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	Y
Brush	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	Y

Agreement= 100%

Table 5*Observational Sheets for IOA - Intervention*

Objects	Session 1			Session 2			Session 3			Session 4		
	OB1	OB2	AGR	OB1	OB2	AGR	OB1	OB3	AGR	OB1	OB2	AGR
Cup	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Ball	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Plate	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Glass	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	Y	Y
Comb	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Car	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Chair	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Bottle	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	Y
Brush	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Phone	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
			8-A, 2-D			9-A, 1-D			9-A, 1-D			10-A, 1-D
	Agreement		80%			90%			90%			100%
	Total agreement		90%									

Table 6*Observation Sheet IOA- Generalization*

Object	Ob1	OB2	AGR	OB12	OB22	AGR2	OB13	OB23	AGR3	OB14	OB24	AGR4
Cup	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Ball	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Plate	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Glass	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	N	Y
Comb	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Car	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Chair	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Bottle	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Brush	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y
Phone	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
			A-9, D-1			A-9, D-1			A-10, D-0			A-10, D-0
	AGR		90%			90%			100%			100%
	Total agreement					95%						

Results

The results of the intervention are given in the graph below (Fig 2). It was seen during the baseline data collection that the child V was

unable to tact for common objects when asked for using "what is this?" (Fig 1). After the intervention, V was able to give the desired answer when the therapist showed him an object and said, "What is this?"

For the first 2 session's full prompt was used in every trial. Here, the child repeated for 2 of the items after the therapist. From the 3rd session, V was able to tact for 3 objects without any prompt and others with a partial prompt. After the 5th session, V was able to tact for 7 objects without prompts and later gave only the desired responses without any prompts.

Generalization probe began after the intervention to see if V was able to use the learned skill and tact for common objects using "what is this?" with another person and in other environments. The second graph (Fig 2) gives the details about the correct responses in the generalized environment. V was able to give the correct response at home and also with other persons when asked using the "what is this?" question.

Figure 1

Data Collection of the Intervention

Figure 2

Data Collection of Intervention and Generalization

Discussion

This study shows that using the supplemental question "What is

this?" is an effective procedure to establish and generalize tact for common objects for a boy with Down's syndrome who would never label the shown object. The results show that prompt fading procedures helped to attain the desired answers. The child needed approximately 10 sessions to be able to tact the shown object when asked for. It was seen during the generalization probe that he was able to tact for the chosen objects in other settings and with other people. Mother was also practicing with the same objects at home as guided by the therapist. The results of this study are similar to the findings of several other studies about the method for teaching tact for common objects. Marchese et al. (2012). Results showed that the question did not have a consistent effect across children: 2 of the 4 children learned tact more efficiently without the question, while the other 2 learned more efficiently with it. Importantly, when tact was later tested without the question, children generally maintained correct labeling regardless of the teaching method.

Limitations of the Study

The limitations of the study could be the fact that teaching one object at a time using several trials over the course of several days is a very time-consuming task, and due to this, the child could learn the skill but be delayed. It would further be interesting to collect data on teaching to tact for other unknown objects in the generalized environment.

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Received February 10, 2026

Revision received February 28, 2026

Accepted March 6, 2026